

Gravimetric Determination of Silver using 4-Vanilideneamino-3-methyl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole

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Manuscript received 1 February 1995, revised 20 July 1995, accepted 7 September 1995

Several sulphur donor ligands have been used for the gravimetric determination of silver¹. Silver(I) being a b-class metal acceptor, it is reasonable to expect a stable complex formation of silver with the ligand because the ligand contains soft-sulphur donor atom. In this communication the use of 4-vanilideneamino-3-methyl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole (VAMMT) for the gravimetric determination of silver in alloys and complexes is described.

Results and Discussion

The reagent VAMMT reacts readily with silver(I) in ammoniacal tartarate media and precipitates silver quantitatively as a white complex. The precipitate being insoluble in hot ethanol unlike the reagent, it can be washed with hot ethanol to remove the excess reagent together with foreign ions. The precipitate is sparingly soluble in organic solvents such as acetone and carbon tetrachloride, but soluble in mineral acids. It is neither hygroscopic nor photosensitive. Thus the method demands no prior precaution in handling the precipitate. Because of its good keeping qualities in dry air the complex can be preserved as such in dry air. The results of elemental analysis of the complex show that it is a 1 : 1 (silver-ligand) complex with the composition Ag(C₁₁H₁₁N₄O₂S). The conversion factor from complex to metal works out to 0.2908. Thus it is quite low as compared to that of the chloride method.

Silver was determined in presence of different cations like Zn^{II}, Pb^{II}, Co^{II}, Mn^{II}, Hg^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} (disodium salt of EDTA was added as masking agent), Al^{III}, Bi^{III} and Zr^{IV} in the concentration range 50–150 mg and different anions such as NO₃⁻, SO₄²⁻, oxalate, acetate and tartarate in the concentration range 500–2500 mg and it was found that these ions do not interfere in the determination of silver. Thermogravimetric analysis showed that the complex does not decompose below 200°.

The results reveal that silver can be determined in the range of 20–98 mg with average error of +0.6%. To assess the accuracy and precision of the method, five determination of silver at 33.54 mg level were carried out with the relative mean deviation 0.0022% and standard deviation of 0.00075.

The proposed method was applied to silver alloys and complexes accurately and its suitability can be seen from the results recorded in the Table 1.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF SILVER IN ALLOYS AND COMPLEX

Sample	Ag present %	Ag found ^a %	Std. dev
Alloys :			
Ag-Cu	75.69 ^a	75.80	0.02
Ag-Cu	88.72 ^a	88.69	0.03
Complexes :			
Ag(C ₃ H ₃ N ₄ OS) ^a	42.80	42.70	0.01
Ag(C ₉ H ₇ N ₄ OS) ^b	32.80	32.64	0.03
Ag(C ₃ H ₃ N ₄ S) ^c	45.30	45.12	0.03

^a Found by chloride method.

^b Silver complex of 4-amino-3-mercapto-1,2,4-triazin(4H)-5-one ^c Silver complex of 4-amino-5-mercapto-6-phenyl-1,2,4-triazin(4H)-5-one ^d Silver complex of 4-amino-5-mercapto-3-methyl-1,2,4-triazole.

Conclusion : The method is precise, simple and rapid. The reagent is selective for Ag in ammoniacal tartarate medium. The silver complex with VAMMT is neither hygroscopic nor photosensitive. The conversion factor Ag complex for silver is very low, 0.2908.

Experimental

The chemicals used were of AnalaR grade.

The reagent VAMMT was prepared by condensing vaniline with 4-amino-3-methyl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole and recrystallised, m.p. 223°. An alcoholic solution of the reagent was prepared.

An aqueous stock solution of silver was prepared from silver nitrate and standardised by the chloride method². Solutions (4–5 mg ml⁻¹) of various metal ions were prepared from their nitrates or sulphates.

Procedure :

An aliquot of the stock solution of silver (containing 20–98 mg Ag) was diluted to ~100 ml, followed by the addition of tartaric acid (1–2 g) and ammonia solution (1 : 1) till the solution became clear and ammoniacal. The solution was then heated to 70–80° and a hot 1% alcoholic solution of the reagent (in slight excess) was added with stirring. The precipitate formed was digested on a water-bath for ~40 min, filtered, washed with hot water and hot ethanol and dried in an air-oven (120–30°) to a constant weight.

NOTE

References

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